

Name: _____

Here is a mid-task, just to see how much knowledge you already have about computing science so far. Your answers to this task will not count for your final score. Nevertheless, let's see how far you get. Good luck!

PART 1

Think about the purpose or outcome of the algorithm specified by the flowchart above. Determine a meaningful name for the method:

PART 2:

Dodo has learned how to lay two kinds of eggs: blue eggs and golden eggs. She uses this capability to decorate the world with various sorts of patterns. Assume that Dodo has the following methods:

Method name	Method Description
layBlueEggAndMove	Lay a blue egg at current position, and then move forward one cell
layGoldEggAndMove	Lay a golden egg at current position, and then move forward one cell
move	Move forward one cell
turnRight	Turn clockwise 90 degrees

Moreover, we extend our flow charts with a REPEAT. The following allows us to express tasks that have to be repeated N (a fixed number) of times:

In this flowchart, method A is executed N times.

For example, the initial and final situations below correspond to the following flowchart:

<p>Initial situation:</p>	
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Now suppose we want Dodo to draw the following pattern (blue eggs are displayed in dark gray; golden eggs in light grey):

Have a look at the four flowcharts below. Each flowchart is executed 4 times. You may assume that the initial position of Dodo is chosen such that the pattern (if produced correctly) will fit in the world (we will come back to this issue later).

Circle the one flowchart which will **NOT** produce the desired pattern.

PART 3:

Assume that Dodo is facing towards the East. Whether the pattern actually fits in the world depends on the algorithm as well as Dodo's initial position.

For each of the correct solutions, indicate the coordinates of the cell in which Dodo should be initially standing. Recall that the upper left corner has coordinates (0,0).

PART 4:

Have a look at Dodo's new decoration.

Notice the (subtle) differences with the pattern in the previous exercise:

- the size of the blue squares has changed;
- the eggs at the corners of the golden square are golden as well. In the previous pattern these were blue;
- Dodo is now initially standing in the upper right corner, facing East.

Use a flowchart to show an algorithm with which Dodo produces the pattern below.

Assume that your algorithm will be repeated 4 times, just like in the previous cases. Hence, your solution should specify one fourth of the complete pattern.

